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Nuriyeva A.Y.

PhD Student at the Department of Azerbaijani Language
Ganja State University

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THE RELIGIOUS CONCEPT "HEAVEN" IN THE HOLY BOOKS AND ITS LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS

Abstract

The article provides an extensive overview of the religious concept of 'heaven' as presented in the Qur'an and the Bible, along with a linguistic analysis of the term. The research delves into various aspects, including cultural and mythological perspectives, as well as contemporary interpretations found in online forums. The study explores the conceptualization of heaven across different cultures and languages, highlighting its symbolic significance and diverse representations.

It has talked about the evolution of the concept within religious and cultural contexts, examining its portrayal in folklore, literature, and contemporary discourse. Additionally, the linguistic analysis delves into semantic universals, individual conceptual spheres, and the cognitive aspects of language usage.

Overall, the article offers a thorough examination of the concept of heaven from religious, cultural, and linguistic perspectives, showcasing its multifaceted nature and its significance in shaping human beliefs and expressions.

Key words: concept, heaven, linguistics, analysis, holy, religious

In Latin, the word "religion" has two meanings: (religio) – 'shrine', and (religare) – 'to unite'. For believers, religion signifies faith in the sacred and unity within an organization characterized by specific behaviors, morals, cults, and rituals (such as the ummah or the church). People read the Qur'an or the Bible and visit temples to find solace, relieve their burdens, and gain inspiration. The Qur'an states: "Strive for bliss in the hereafter, in the refuge of Allah!" (Surah 3) [6]. Similarly, the Apostle Paul writes: "Faith is the substance of things hoped for and the evidence of things not seen" (Hebrews 11:1) [5].

The introduction of Christianity to Slavic culture brought new concepts, including "Hell" and "Paradise". Many scholars believe that these concepts did not exist among pagans [3]. The religious depiction of Heaven was not detailed and was similar to that of Hell, so without visual representations, people adapted these images to fit their existing worldview at national, group, and individual levels, integrating them into their reality. Among the Slavs, church ideas about hell and heaven often merged with folk traditions or coexisted with them, sometimes contradicting each other in local customs and individual beliefs [8]. Paradise is depicted as an ever-blooming garden without death, pain, or aggression.

The concepts of "Hell" and "Paradise" in folklore were studied by S.S. Vorontsov [10, p. 28-32]. The vague images of hell and paradise intrigue not only scholars but also many modern internet users, who share their own ideas about these places. We analyzed the responses from forum members to questions such as: How do you imagine heaven and hell, as well as God and the devil? How do you imagine hell and where do your ideas about it come from? What is paradise? What is hell for you? How do you imagine paradise? Do you think heaven and hell exist?

The data collection method used was continuous sampling. Responses from individuals who denied the existence of hell and heaven or simply quoted others were excluded.

In most cases, paradise is described as a garden with nectar, ambrosia, eternal summer, angels, and pleasant music. It is often referred to as the Kingdom of Heaven, Eden, or Paradise. Paradise is envisioned as a door to summer, an open terrace by the sea, reminiscent of a Bounty advertisement. It is a place where the soul feels good and calm, in a divine sense of goodness, much like the comfort of a mother's embrace during childhood. Paradise is depicted as a heavenly place, closer to God, part of the afterlife with eternal spring, beautiful and fragrant, devoid of melancholy, sadness, snow, or storms. It is believed to exist in everyone's heart.

Quotations were taken verbatim, preserving the original spelling and punctuation of the authors (users).

In English culture, paradise is represented by the synonymous terms Heaven and Paradise. English-speaking individuals depict Heaven and Paradise as places of blessing where good people go after death, characterized by peace and bliss. Heaven is often described as an unbelievably beautiful world, the existence of which some may doubt.

In conclusion, the image of paradise is largely consistent among those who answered the related questions. The conceptsphere of hell and heaven is diverse. To visualize it, consider its components through the following elements: place, characteristics (such as smell, light, conditions, sound), functions, structure, personosphere, purposes, and whether it involves torture or reward.

A place can be considered paradise if it has good people and water (though humorously, this is what hell is said to lack). In paradise, there is no hunger or bothersome in-laws, but there is good football. Paradise

varies across different religions; for instance, what is considered heaven in Christianity might be seen as hell for the Vikings.

Paradise is typically associated with coolness, spaciousness, eternal greenery, comfort, prosperity, cleanliness, peace, radiance, pleasant aroma, silence, melody, and birdsong. Conversely, hell is characterized by heat, tightness, emptiness, stuffiness, disorder, dirt, quarrels, noise, groaning, stench, and darkness.

The function of paradise is straightforward: to create special conditions for eternal enjoyment as a reward for the righteous. Hell and heaven, however, are closely interconnected. The connection can be maintained through embassies, telephones, TV, personal communication, and letters, and one can appeal to God for help against the destructive actions of sinners affecting devils.

Unlike hell, heaven lacks a clear structure and offers limited activities—such as admiring nature, singing, and praying. The personosphere of paradise includes Allah, the Lord God, the Creator, angels, archangels (such as Archangel Gabriel), the righteous, and historical and religious figures (like Adam and Eve before their fall). People enter heaven through good deeds, heroic acts, or sometimes by accident.

Therefore, the objectification of the concepts "Hell" and "Paradise" in folk representations is slightly different, as shown by the number of identified lexical representatives forming the lexical-semantic paradigm of these concepts. At the lexical level, these concepts are characterized by the feature of "habitat", expressed through thematic subgroups like "in this world" and "in the next world". The "state of mind", a fundamental feature according to dictionary definitions, is represented in internet jokes through various lexical means. This indicates that the concepts of "Hell" and "Paradise" are deeply rooted in the national worldview of Russian and English users, reflecting a significant element of the Christian heritage.

The concept is always linked to a linguistic personality, essentially authorizing an "impersonal", objective worldview in relation to an ethno-semantic personality, which serves as a basic national-cultural prototype for a native speaker, embedded in the semantic system of natural language.

In contemporary linguistics, it is established that there are several semantic universals, though their exact number is not determined. These universals are considered "fundamental human concepts," and the semantic elements (primitives) form the basis of all languages. These elements correspond to the concept of lexico-semantic universals, which are common nomination mechanisms across languages, reflecting consistent relationships between linguistic meaning and form. Both in the universal and idio-ethnic worldview, distinctions are made between the material (real) and spiritual (mental), empirical and rational, and spatial and temporal worlds. Within an idio-ethnic linguistic worldview, there is a contrast between the national linguistic worldview and those defined by social spheres.

In an individual linguistic worldview, and in the texts of a single author (the macrotext of the idiostyle),

it is possible to identify more specific worlds: the external, which reflects surrounding realities (including fantastic or mythical worlds), and the internal, which is primarily evaluative and axiological, and often fragmented. This internal world represents the individual's thoughts, feelings, and will, which do not always align.

The most distinct opposition is seen between the universal, highly abstract worldview reflected across different languages, and the individual worldview reflected in an individual's speech or texts—whether a native speaker or a creative artist—thus creating a unique artistic world. This unique artistic world, recognized as a crucial category in modern literary criticism, is characterized by the system of all images and motifs within a text.

Linguistic worlds result from the human process of organizing and classifying the chaos of the real world, leading to a hierarchy of linguistic worldviews. Each world corresponds to specific linguistic means and a conceptual core. The signals of multiple worlds and the concrete world are most clearly expressed in words-concepts. Each word-concept serves as the name of a semantic field within different lexical-semantic variants of polysemantic words, in vocabulary and phraseology, proverbs and sayings, and idiomatic expressions.

To depict the worldview reflected in language, one should first consider a system of concepts that most accurately represent this worldview, based on the principle of "peaks." Concepts are special mental constructs formed from the unique division of the linguistic picture of the world into specific micro-worlds, corresponding to the "semantics of possible worlds," where the primary creative unit is the word-concept—the name of a particular linguocultural field.

As a kind of "algebraic" expression of meaning, which we use in both written and spoken language, the concept, due to its substitutive function, facilitates linguistic communication.

When discussing words and concepts, we must consider the individual, as the breadth and richness of a person's cultural experience enhance the potential of concepts. Each person possesses unique cultural experiences, knowledge, and skills, which enrich the meanings of words and concepts. Thus, we can refer to the individual conceptual sphere of a linguistic personality, represented by concepts.

Concepts expand the possibilities for co-creation and interpretation, varying according to context and personal experience.

Comparing linguistic concepts, we concluded that depending on the study aspect, there are universal concepts (universological study), linguocultural concepts (linguocultural study), and unique concepts (personal study). The first category consists of 'fundamental universal concepts,' a limited set that is key to understanding the national mentality and its unique worldview.

Any lexical unit whose meaning serves as a method or form of semantic representation can be included in this category. These correspond to the 'semantic elements' (primitives) of A. Vezhbitskaya, which can be identified through thorough analysis of

any language, and protoconcepts ('noemas') used in comparison and translation [9].

Thus, the concept is defined as a plan for the content of a linguistic sign, encompassing subject correlation, all meaningful communicative information, paradigmatic, syntagmatic, and derivational connections, as well as the sign's pragmatic information due to its expressive and communicative functions. Additionally, it includes the cognitive memory of the word associated with its original purpose and the language's system of spiritual values.

From a cultural perspective, concepts are stereotypical images characteristic of a specific linguistic consciousness. These concepts represent the most general, abstracted, yet concretely represented idea of an "object" within the set of all nationally and culturally marked valence bonds. They do not form a conceptual sphere but occupy a specific area within it—a conceptual area. As part of the linguistic picture of the world, they form the cognitive basis of the semantics of standard formations that define the 'internal form of the language' [2], reflecting and interpreting the world within the national-linguistic consciousness. They determine the uniqueness of a particular linguistic worldview.

For structuring national-cultural worldviews, "worldview concepts" (ethno-eidemas), which can persist in linguistic consciousness long after their actual disappearance, and microconcepts, eidemodictors (onomatopoetic representations), are key components. These elements form part of the semantic field of a given ethno-eidema, resulting from the division and detailed interpretation by the national-linguistic (linguo-creative) consciousness of the corresponding ethno-eidema [1].

Concepts can differ significantly across languages and among different speakers of the same language, as they are influenced by individual worldviews. Therefore, the most intriguing aspect is the individual psychological perspective, where personal authorial concepts or text-specific concepts hold particular significance. Thus, a concept can be understood, first, as a linguocultural unit representing collective conscious/unconscious knowledge, which is linguistically expressed and marked by ethnocultural specificity, including the ethnocultural authorization of semantic units [11]. Second, it is a fundamental cognitive essence [7] that links meaning to the word used.

The study, "Aspects of Interpretation of the Concepts "Heaven" and "Hell"," provides a multidimensional description of these concepts, examining them from cultural, religious, and linguistic perspectives within the worldview of native Russian speakers. These concepts encapsulate the mythological, religious, and universal ideas of the world order. The analysis also explains the choice of these concepts based on their significance in the linguistic worldview from the 11th to the 20th centuries, considering their semantic content and functioning, using data from historical, etymological, explanatory, synonymous, and associative dictionaries.

Research has shown that these concepts include not only knowledge about heaven and hell, representing the entirety of their meanings, but also encompass the full set of connotative elements evident in their associative-verbal networks, as revealed through

conceptual analysis. Observations of the compatibility of the words 'hell' and 'heaven' with various attributes and predicates uncovered deep associative features of these concepts, comprising implicit (metaphorized) substantive lexical parameters, or *gestalts*.

The concept of 'heaven' encompasses universal knowledge about these realms, based on the mythological idea of these polar regions where souls go after death, depending on their actions during life: sinners who violated moral laws go to hell, while saints and the pious go to heaven.

For instance, in the minds of the ancient Slavs, paradise was seen as a place where good forces were concentrated, a realm where the souls of the deceased who had chosen their paths in life resided. The ancient Slavs believed that the freedom to choose between Good and Evil was a divine gift given at birth. Individuals were free to choose their life paths and bear responsibility for their choices. Heaven, as the final realm of the life process, bore the mark of eternity: blessed eternity.

The mythological worldviews of different peoples reveal that there was no strict division between hell and paradise. The spheres where souls went after death were seen as extensions of the natural, earthly (or underground) world, which had a very conventional division into realms of good and evil. Furthermore, the underworld, the world of the dead, was an integral part of the world of the living, constantly interacting with it. The fate of the dead was closely intertwined with the fate of the living.

This analysis allows us to identify common features of the concept of "heaven":

A place where Good is concentrated, without a clear spatial position but separated by a river; in paradise, there are forces of goodness, eternal prosperity, and peace (Belbog, Zhiva, angels, etc.).

Attributes: in paradise, there is coolness, a wonderful garden with beautiful plants, and daylight.

A state prepared for mortals forever - a gift where the righteous in paradise experience bliss.

In religious development, the concepts of "hell" and "paradise" became fundamental to theological doctrines about the afterlife, Good, Evil, and the Last Judgment awaiting everyone after death.

Summarizing various mythological and religious ideas about heaven, it is evident that the concept of "heaven" has a mythological nature. It has a conceptual structure characterized by spatio-temporal localization (place, phase in time), a systemic nature of internal structure (with primary features and objects that interact, and secondary ones), and determinism (the external and internal manifestation of the state of the subject located in this space, with direct and inverse conditionality).

An analysis of the typical linguistic representations of the concept of 'heaven,' based on etymological, historical, and modern explanatory, phraseological dictionaries, as well as dictionaries of synonyms and antonyms, shows that the concept has a common mythological nature. It possesses a set of differential features such as spatial and temporal localization, attributiveness, causal relationships, and role settings assumed by subjects in heaven. The concept of "paradise" is represented in the linguistic picture of the world in local and hedonistic cognitive models, each corresponding to a specific frame:

'heavenly paradise,' 'primitive earthly paradise' (local model variations), and 'paradise - living conditions' (hedonic model).

The exploration of the word "heaven" reveals a rich tapestry of meanings, allowing for the delineation of its conceptual framework and the modeling of its semantic domains. At its core, "paradise" signifies a realm after death, with adjacent zones encompassing notions like Eden, earthly existence, and the inhabitants of paradise such as God, angels, and the righteous. Themes of righteousness leading to bliss form a central nexus, while the periphery encompasses elements like nature, beauty, and tranquility. This conceptual structure, with its core, perinuclear, and peripheral zones, mirrors similar gestalt formations across various linguistic expressions, underscoring the universality of the concept.

Analyzing the semantic content of a concept involves delving into its denotative and connotative meanings, its interconnections within language, and the contextual knowledge it embodies. The incorporation of background knowledge within the concept's structure enables diverse interpretations, reflecting individual linguistic personalities. Artistic concepts, derived from literary works, offer unique insights into authors' worldviews, with the texts themselves serving as environments for these concepts to flourish.

In the 20th-century artistic landscape, the concept of "hell" assumes nuanced connotations, influenced by authors' distinct stylistic choices and aesthetic philosophies, particularly in the realm of postmodernism.

Focusing on functional-cognitive analysis within literary texts, our objective is to discern the linguistic tools employed to convey ideological, thematic, and aesthetic content, along with the criteria guiding their selection. Our findings highlight how authors' strategic approaches, aligned with their thematic intentions, dictate the utilization of diverse linguistic and artistic techniques, shaping a meta-language that facilitates interaction between author and reader. This meta-language encapsulates the multifaceted perspectives, heightened sensitivity, and auditory receptivity of both author and characters, enriching the textual experience.

The primary methods for conveying the artistic worldview encompass metaphor in its myriad forms, alliteration (which, for Nabokov, extends to conveying extralinguistic content), allusions, and reminiscences. Metaphor, especially in context, assumes a pivotal role as a reflection of the author's stance, serving not only as a vehicle for individual meanings but also as a deliberate subversion of logical and semantic norms, purposefully manipulated by the author. It stands as the principal artistic and visual tool, exerting a central influence on the author's narrative strategy. Notably, the various types of metaphor employed by the author may not always possess overt structural delineations; instead, diffusion, mutual substitution, and fusion characterize Nabokov's use of metaphor, likening the richness of linguistic expression to the allure of life itself [4, p. 11-12].

The manifold implications surrounding the concept of "heaven" within the text significantly broaden its conceptual scope, introducing novel interpretations and verbal expressions. Textual concepts serve to interconnect and interdependently shape the language's worldview, manifesting through a flow of meanings that delineate concepts. The distinctive functioning of the concept "heaven" within literary language allowed for the identification of several processes within its structural framework: firstly, the emergence of structural lacunae within concepts, leading to the fragmentation of the postmodernist artistic worldview; secondly, heterogeneity, wherein various semiotic codes coalesce without compromising conceptual integrity; thirdly, the perpetual challenge of clear concept structuring due to ongoing internal determinations among components; fourthly, the prevalence of fragmentation and discontinuity; and finally, deviations from the conventional structure of the concept. The eidemodistintor, whether within its core or periphery, may either persist in "old" meanings while undergoing redistributions within the structure or adopt "new" interpretations, thereby extending into other semantic domains.

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